

1 **LMX1b is a component homeobox in the TE specification program.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Lmx1b
9 as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo. We present evidence in the
10 same report an Lmx1b-associated non-coding RNA also with functions in trophectoderm fate choice
11 decisions.

12 Citations

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